

AN UPDATE ON THE SOCIAL PROFILE OF GREEK ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA (Version 2)

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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to provide a partial social profile of Greek Orthodox in Australia. It is derived from the national census in 2021. There are 390,963 Greek Orthodox in Australia. Around 37% of Greek Orthodox have at least one parent born overseas. Whereas Greek is a language used at home by 53% of Greek Orthodox, amongst Greek Orthodox 39% speak only English. The median level of income of Greek Orthodox is in the range \$650-\$799 per week. Some 43% of Greek Orthodox are married and 90% of these are through a registered marriage.

Keywords

Greek Orthodox, Australia. social background, census

I. INTRODUCTION

There are always stereotypes around ethnic and religious groups. They provide a “shorthand” description that takes into consideration many assumed or observed features of a group, such as language, religion, marriage and socioeconomic status. No doubt, stereotypes also exist within ethnic and religious groups about themselves. The purpose of the report is merely to provide some insight into the Greek Orthodox community. No claim is made that it is a complete analysis.

The information in this report is derived from the national census in 2021 (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2022) in response to the optional question on one’s religion (“What is the person’s religion?”). In 2021, 93.1% of the population answered the religious question (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2022). At the same time the Census collected other social information that are of wider relevance to religion.

The report is a continuation of a program of earlier research into Greek Orthodox in Australia. It updates previous reports of the 2016 Census data (Athanasou 2022a, 2022b) and follows on from a recent analysis of the 2021 national Census (Athanasou 2022c).

II. BACKGROUND

There are 390.963 people in Australia who indicated that they are Greek Orthodox. Possibly there are some who did not answer the question accurately in the Census. For instance, they may have indicated “Orthodox” or “Christian” instead of “Greek Orthodox”. It is possible that there is some underestimate but this is still the most valid information available on Greek Orthodox in Australia.

The 390,963 who indicated that they were Greek Orthodox are 1.54% in a population of 25,422,788. At this level the margin of error is very small. Considering sampling error, there is a 99% level of confidence that the actual number is up to 398,391. The general point is that this figure provides a sound basis for the size of the Greek Orthodox population in Australia.

The following sections consider topics such as ancestry, language spoken at home, English proficiency, income and marital or household status. At the time of writing data on education and occupation had not been released.

What is the overseas ancestry of Greek Orthodox?

It is not a remarkable statement that Greek Orthodox in Australia are a migrant community. At present, 62% (all percentages rounded) of Greek Orthodox have both parents born overseas. This will change over time and now 24% have both parents born in Australia. If one adds those whose father only was born overseas or those whose mother only was born overseas then this rises to 37%. Figure 1 outlines the parental backgrounds of Greek Orthodox.

Figure 1. Parental background of Greek Orthodox.

Is Greek spoken at home?

The Census assessed familiarity with the Greek language, which is an important component for maintenance of cultural heritage.

In Australia, Greek is a language used at home by 206,834 Greek Orthodox out of a total of 390,963 (i.e., 53%). Of course, this does not show fluency in or the extent of knowledge of Greek.

Table 1

English language proficiency

English proficiency	Proportion
Speaks English only	39%
Other language and speaks English: Very well	39%
Other language and speaks English: Well	12%
Other language and speaks English: Not well	9%
Other language and speaks English: Not at all	1%
Not stated	1%

Are Greek Orthodox proficient in the English language?

Equally important for educational, social and vocational adjustment in Australia is the knowledge of English. A person’s self-assessed proficiency in English was indicated in the Census (“How well does the person speak English?”).

There are, just under 40,000 Greek Orthodox who do not speak English well or do not speak English at all (see second and third last rows of Table 1). On the other hand, 39% speak only English. It means that 78% of the Greek Orthodox population consider themselves as very proficient in English.

Figure 2. Greek Orthodox income levels.

How is income distributed across the Greek Orthodox?

It is not clear how the median level of income of Greek Orthodox is perceived in the wider community. In any event, the median was in the range \$650-\$799 for those 299,368 Greek Orthodox who listed an income level. The breakdown of incomes of those who are Greek Orthodox is shown in Figure 2 and it appears evenly distributed, except at the extremes.

What do we know about the marital and household status of Greek Orthodox?

The registered marital status of Greek Orthodox for whom this question is applicable is mainly married or widowed: 43% are married, 7% are widowed, 3% are separated, 7% divorced and 26% have never married.

Of those 43% whose social status is listed as “married”, 90% of them are through a registered marriage and 10% in a de facto marriage. This compares with 79% for all other Australians in a registered marriage and 20% in a de facto marriage. The median number of children born was two children (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Greek Orthodox – number of children born.

III. CONCLUSIONS

The information from the national Census in 2021 provided the opportunity for a formal and official social picture of Greek Orthodox. The available information indicates that there are many potential variations in the profile of Greek Orthodox members in Australia. There is no uniform stereotype or characterisation. It is a complex mixture of ancestry, linguistic background and family status.

There is however a modal type. For want of a better word, it comprises the most common characterisation. A summary is attempted in following paragraph.

The most typical Greek Orthodox is a minority member of the Australian population. He or she has parents who in all likelihood were born overseas but one in three now have at least one parent who is Australian born. Quite a few Greek Orthodox say that Greek is spoken at home but the quality or standard of the Greek language is not determined. Just on 40% speak only English. There are still some 40,000 who do not speak English at all but over time this number must decline. In terms of

income, Greek Orthodox are not particularly well-off. The median level of income is \$650-\$799. The registered marital status of Greek Orthodox for whom this question is applicable is mainly married or widowed. There is a significant number divorced (7%) or in de facto marriages (10%). Same-sex relationships hardly register on the radar (0.6%).

It seems difficult to stereotype Greek Orthodox, except to say that for the most part they are mainstream and possibly more conservative than the overall population in their norms and mores (e.g., marriage). Greekness (e.g., language or ancestry) is a component of the identity of Greek Orthodox but it is changing. Overall, it is useful to have access to such official statistics that can dispel any myths or misconceptions of Greek Orthodox.

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